

PASTDARG'OM TUMANI TARIXIY VA ZAMONAVIY TURIZM IMKONIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya. *Maqolada Samarqand viloyati, Pastdarg'om tumanida mavjud bo'lgan tarixiy obidalarni va tabiiy rekratsiyon resurslaridan turizm maqsadlarda samarali foydalanish. Hududlarni rivojlantirish, yangi ish o'rinlarini yaratish, aholining daromatlarini va turmush darajasini oshirish, tumanning investitsiyaviy jozibadorligini oshirishni, ta'minlovchi strategik tarmoqlarida biri sifatida rivojlantirish bo'yicha kompleks chora tadbirlar amalga oshirish bo'yicha takliflar kiritilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Turistik hududlar, qayerlar, yomlar, turizm, sayyohlik, iqtisodiyot, Buyuk ipak yo'li.*

HISTORICAL AND MODERN TOURISM OPPORTUNITIES OF PASTDARGOM DISTRICT

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Abstract. *In the article, the effective use of historical monuments and natural recreation resources in Pastdargom district of Samarkand region for cultural purposes. Proposals have been made to develop the regions, create new jobs, increase*

the incomes and living standards of the population, increase the investment attractiveness of the district, and implement comprehensive measures to develop the district as one of the strategic sectors that ensure the investment and attractiveness of the district.

Key words: *Tourist areas, places, holidays, tourism, tourism, economy, the Great Silk Road.*

Enter. Pastdargom district of Samarkand region was one of the ancient settlements and settlements of our country. The second component of the toponym is Dargom - an ancient canal, a ditch, coming out of the Zarafshan river. Its length is about 100 kilometers. It starts from the "First May" dam of the Zarafshan river and ends in the Ulus desert. Historical sources report that the ditch was dug during the Kushan dynasty in the 5th-4th centuries BC. In the map compiled by Claudius Ptolemy (II century), the name of this stream is mentioned in the form of Darhomonius. The first component of the toponym Darg means "long", and the second part -om is a modified form of -ob. Because "b" and "m" sounds are exchanged. In ancient times, the Great Silk Road passed through the territory of Pastdargom district. All countries have their own tourism destinations. We know that the directions of tourism are multifaceted, for example, in Egypt there is more direction of architecture, and in Turkey, gastronomic tourism, mountain tourism is developed in most European countries. Accordingly, as a result of large-scale reforms carried out in Uzbekistan in recent years, great work has been done in many directions of tourism, including pilgrimage tourism, gastronomic tourism, architectural tourism. In particular, their renovation during the jubilees of thinkers plays a decisive role in this. In recent years, Uzbekistan has risen from 34th place to 9th place in the world ranking of pilgrimage tourism.

The basis of the part of the historical monuments of Pastdargom is considered to be ancient steps and saghanas. Currently, the permanent population of Pastdargom district is 337,990 people (2023), and 25% of them are unemployed. The tourism

opportunities of Basdargom district are highly valued due to its sufficient internal strength, sufficient qualified personnel, good supply of water resources, 1-2 km wide Zarafshan river in the northern part, and this place is crowded with people during the summer chill. to be

The main part. 4 in Pasdargom - Ashik father's shrine, Amir Temur's shrine, Karovul hills (Yomlar), which have almost preserved the ancient defense objects, preserved cisterns, and special mineral water fountains and hot springs rich in mineral salts from the climatic resources of the river. Nowadays, thousands of people come to see these places. Especially in the hot summer months, 100-200 people come to the part of the Zarafshon river that passes through Pastdargom district, and even more. But for some objective and subjective reasons, the number of tourists and visitors is decreasing year by year. In order to increase the tourism potential of Pastdargom district, it is possible to increase the tourism potential by modernizing the existing historical and natural climate resources, establishing advertising and special sanatoriums, and creating amenities for pilgrims. Pastdargom district has a history of several thousand years. Local linguists and toponymists explain the origin of the name Pastdargom tuam as the bottom of the river (Dargom). In fact, the Dargom canal, located in the lower part of the Zarafshan river, flows through the territory of the district. On September 9, 1141, the battle between the Seljuks and the Karakhitas took place on the banks of the Dargom River in the Kotvan steppe, and historians say that "... 30,000 Seljuks died in the battle, 10,000 were swept away by the Dargom River." The name of the river is also found in "Boburnoma". [1] The topography of the district is a flat plain, sloping from east to west. The surface of the earth is made up of Tertiary sedimentary rocks. The upper part is covered by alluvial deposits from Zarafshan and its tributaries. The south-east of the district is occupied by the western end of the Zafarfshan mountain ranges. The highest point reaches 2204 meters.[2] The population is mainly Uzbeks, as well as representatives of Tajik, Russian, Tatar, Korean and other nationalities. The average population density is 504 people per 1 km². [3]

There are 128 general education schools (2023), 3 vocational colleges, 1 art lyceum under the Republican Art Academy, an art college opened in cooperation between Uzbekistan and Korea, 2 music schools, 59 libraries, 22 clubs, houses and palaces of culture in the Lower Dargom district. - Niyat and recreational parks, 22 folk theaters, 6 folk ensembles operate. There are 12 stadiums, 890 sports fields, sports clubs for national wrestling, karate, real-aikido and other sports in the district. [4] Tashkent - Dushanba, Tashkent - Karshi trains pass through the territory of the district. Buses run on Kattakurgan-Zuma-Samarkand, Samarkand-Sazaghon-Zom, Zuma-Khoncharvok and other routes. Buses traveling along the Tashkent-Urganch, Tashkent-Navoi routes also pass through the district. A paved road was constructed between Juma and Sazagon. Since 1931, the newspaper of the district "Past Dargom Haqiqiti" has been published. Most of the local population make a living by providing services and farming.

It is expedient to increase tourism in the territory of the district, primarily domestic tourists. The reason is that there are not enough opportunities to serve foreign tourists. For example; there are no hotels, parks, modern tourism facilities. The main aspects that can attract the attention of the population of the country are Islamic shrines, recreational resources, and historical objects. Nevertheless, there are factors that hinder the development of the tourism industry.

About some shortcomings in the case of Pastedargom district;

- the fact that almost all objects are located on the road leads to the development of tourism. Separate buses are organized for tourists. But there are no cars. The number of light vehicles should be increased.

- Historical-architectural and religious pilgrimage tourism is developed in the district. Tourists who visit the region will definitely get bored in this situation. If recreation parks and modern buildings are built in this area, which are different from other recreation parks with their nationality, this will increase the flow of tourists.

- it is necessary to pay more attention to the organization of the activities of public eating places in the district. Because every region has its own national dishes, the local

population has several national dishes as well. For example, Europeans he first studies the food he sees for the first time, sees the preparation technology, and then eats it. Maybe they want to eat their European food or maybe there are vegetarians among the tourists. Taking this into account, if restaurants and cafes prepare at least one type of food from different countries, if their service level improves, if the needs of tourists are met in time, tourists visiting the district will be satisfied. This causes the flow of tourists to increase

- in general, it is necessary to introduce a wi-fi system in places visited by tourists.

CONCLUSION

Pastdargom district, which has a history of many thousand years, should be turned into a real tourism center. Due to its unique historical potential, special emphasis is placed on increasing the attractiveness of pilgrimage tourism. Pilgrimage is not just a journey, it is an opportunity for self-awareness, a path to spiritual purification, hope, prayer and wish fulfillment, faith.

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